

Creativity of Higher Secondary Students with Regard to Nature of School

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Abstract:

Present study was undertaken to examine the level of creativity and creativity among boys', girls' and co-education school higher secondary students. For that purpose, 299 higher secondary students were selected randomly from ten different schools of Tirunelveli district out of which 36 were taken from boys' schools, 35 were taken from girls' schools and the remaining 228 were taken from co-education schools. Creativity questionnaire by Geoffrey Petty for higher secondary students was used to examine the level of creativity among the higher secondary students. The result of descriptive analysis revealed that 69.4% of boys' school higher secondary students have high level of creativity. The result of inferential analysis (ANOVA) revealed that there is significant difference in creativity of higher secondary students with regard to nature of school. From the result of Scheffe test and mean differences, it was also found that the boys' school higher secondary students have more creativity than the girls' school and co-education school higher secondary students.

Keywords: ANOVA, Co-education, Creativity, Descriptive, Inferential, Scheffe

1. Introduction

M.J.Liven (1978) said that Creativity is the ability to discover new solutions to problems or to produce new ideas, inventions or works of art. It is a special form of thinking, a way of viewing the world and interacting with it in a manner different from that of the general population. According to Wilson, Guilford and Christensen (1974) The creative process is any process by which something new is produced-an idea or an object including a new form or arrangement of old elements. The new creation must contribute to the solution of some problems. (Dr.S.Sabu, 2012:110) Teachers come across many instances, when a student's behaviour is surprisingly different from others while discussing about a controversial problem. Such students are talented ones, having special capabilities in tackling problems and producing original, distinct and unique solutions. To promote such as ability in the students, the teachers have to take special pains. The main responsibility of the teacher is to provide situations and encouragement to induce young people to express themselves in a novel and original way. Everyone can draw, paint, sing or write a theme and the teacher's task is to guide and encourage young people to aim higher, and to promote creative effort and achievement. The following points are suggested to help the teachers in teaching their subject creatively. (Bhatnagar, Bhatnagar, Bhatnagar, 2006: 331) According to Sharma (1991), students of co-educational schools were found to be more creative than those of unisex schools. Mahender Reddy Sarsani (2006) found that there are no significant differences among the students from girls, boys and co-educational schools on verbal originality, fluency, flexibility and total verbal creativity.

2. Significance of the Study

As human beings we have an extraordinary power – the ability to imagine things outside of our current experiences and to express them in forms that other people can engage with and grasp. No other species on Earth has this ability. World is changing faster than ever before and the people facing challenges that are unprecedented. These sorts of challenges require innovative ideas and approaches. As such, many

governments, companies and people are interested in innovation. In this technological world, creativity plays a main role in school education. A creative process may begin with a flash of a new idea or with a hunch. It may just start as noodling around with a problem, getting some fresh ideas along the way. It's a process, not a single event, and genuine creative processes involve critical thinking as well as imaginative insights and fresh ideas. Scientists have wondered for some time if people who think "creatively" are able to somehow think differently from those who seem to think in a more methodical fashion. However, many researchers have argued that what we call "creative thought" and "non-creative thought" are really not two different things. If that were true, then people who are thought of as "creative" would not actually think in a fundamentally different way from those who are thought of as uncreative. Creativity is a trait that discriminates a creative individual from non-creative ones. It is a individual differences. Considering the contribution of creativity to social progress and to the self-realization and self-esteem of the individual it is obvious that encouragement and promotion of creativity among young people should be a major aim and responsibility of the school. As has been pointed out earlier creativity is not given only to a few but in a smaller or greater measure is well within the reach of every individual. We do not divide people into creative and non-creative but we range them along a continuum, some are more creative and some are less creative, and it is the creation of a small minority which achieves a high standard of originality, uniqueness, and objectivity and wins universal acclaim. The school cannot plant or produce creativity among children but it can certainly help to kindle what-spark of creativity nature has gifted them into a brighter glow. According to Mahender Reddy Sarsani (2006), the behaviour of individuals by the interaction between their personal characteristics and those of the institution. Forehead and Gilmer (1969) have defined 'behaviour' as a function of "function of the interaction between personal characteristics and environmental variables". They have considered 'climate' as a set of organizational properties, which may influence the individuals in an organization. Schools are classified as boys', girls' and co-educational on the basis of sex of the pupils' population. Thus, the study of creativity with respect to nature of school becomes necessary.

3. Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the level of creativity of higher secondary students with regard to nature of school.
2. To find out whether there is any significant difference in creativity of higher secondary students with regard to nature of school.

4. Hypothesis

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in creativity of higher secondary students with regard to nature of school.

5. Method of Study

The present study aims at finding out the creativity of higher secondary students. Therefore, the normative survey method has been used in the study.

6. Sample

The study was conducted on a sample of 299 higher secondary students from the higher secondary schools of Tirunelveli district out of which 36 were taken from boys' schools, 35 were taken from girls' schools and the remaining 228 were taken from co-education schools. The random sampling technique was used by the investigator for the selection of the sample.

7. Tool Used

In order to measure the creativity of higher secondary students, the creativity questionnaire by Geoffrey Petty was used. The author established the reliability (0.78) of the tool.

8. Statistical Techniques Used

Mean, Standard deviation, F-test and Post – hoc test (Scheffe test) were used to analyse the data.

9. Descriptive Analysis

Objective: To find out the level of creativity of higher secondary students with regard to nature of school.

Table :1 Level of creativity of higher secondary students with regard to nature of school

Variable	Nature of school	Low		Average		High	
		Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Creativity	Boys	7	19.4	4	11.1	25	69.4
	Girls	16	45.7	14	40.0	5	14.3
	Co-education	70	30.7	79	34.6	79	34.6

With regard to boys' school, 19.4% of students have low level, 11.1% of students have average level and 69.4% of them have high level of creativity. With regard to girls' school, 45.7% of students have low level, 40.0% of them have average level and 14.3% of them have high level of creativity. With regard to co-education school, 30.7% of students have low level, 34.6% of them have average level and 34.6% of them have high level of creativity.

10. Inferential Analysis

H_0 : There is no significant difference in creativity of higher secondary students with regard to nature of school.

Table : 2 ANOVA showing the significant difference in the creativity and its dimension among higher secondary students with regard to nature of school

Variable	Source variance	Sum of square	df	Mean square	Calculated F - value	Table value	Remarks
Creativity	Between	245.050	2	122.525	8.162	3.00	S
	Within	4443.372	296	15.011			

(Table value - 3.00 for df (2,296) at 5% level of significance)

It is inferred from above table that the calculated F value (8.162) is greater than the table value (3.00) for df (2, 296) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It shows that there is significant difference in creativity of higher secondary students with regard to nature of school.

Table: 3 Scheffe test result shows the significance difference in the creativity of higher secondary students with respect to nature of school

Mean value of creativity			
Boys	Girls	Co-education	Remarks
31.1389	27.6286	—	*
31.1389	—	28.7105	*
—	27.6286	28.7105	—

The scheffe test result shows that there is significant difference between boys and girls school higher secondary students in their creativity. And also there is significant difference between boys and co-education school higher secondary students in their creativity.

11. Findings and Conclusion

The result of descriptive analysis revealed that 69.4% of boys' school higher secondary students have high level of creativity. The result of inferential analysis (F-test) revealed that there is significant difference in creativity of higher secondary students with regard to nature of school. From the result of scheffe test and mean differences, it was also found that the boys' school higher secondary students have more creativity than the girls' school and co-education school higher secondary students. It may be due to the fact that the boys in the boys' school setting, they may not worry about what the girls might

think. And also they may express their ability and do more creative activities without any hesitation in boys' schools. Getting attracted to the opposite sex in adolescence is a normal and natural phenomenon. Such kind of sexual attraction is not affect the higher secondary students inside the boys schools campus. Though both genders develop increased capacity and interest in sexuality at adolescent stage, the boys are sexually more distracted by their opposite sex than girls.

References

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